

›Short name	Social acceptability (Cf. social acceptance)	Long name	The emergence of social acceptance
Geographical scope	Local level, community level		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	Social acceptability is a combination of social acceptance and social support. Social acceptability ¹ is a more democratic and socially inclusive concept than social acceptance, which is a top-down concept and mainly evaluates whether stakeholders and laypeople are not actively opposing or contesting a technology. Social acceptability pertains to engagement of local communities in developing CCS projects ³⁻⁶ .		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Similar projects are becoming central for renewable energy development • How a local community can benefit from CC(U)S projects directly (i.e. social acceptability relates to benefit perception as well). Here benefit perceptions are different: tackling climate change is a primary perception for some, whereas economic benefits for others or both (i.e. tackling climate change and economic benefits)⁷ • Local communities initiate CC(U)S projects⁸⁻⁹ 		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal instruments are non-existence • A complex issue to engage local communities in CC(U)S projects cf. renewable energy, not least for the issues such as liability, high costs and so forth.¹⁰ 		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Batel, S., Devine-Wright, P., & Tangeland, T. (2013): Social acceptance of low carbon energy and associated infrastructures: A critical discussion. <i>Energy Policy</i>, 58, 1-5. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2013.02.039 • Witte, K. (2021): Social acceptance of carbon capture and storage (CCS) from industrial applications. <i>Sustainability</i>, 13(21), 12278. https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112278 • Whitmarsh, L.; Xenias, D.; Jones, C.R. (2019): Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage. <i>Palgrave Communications</i>, 5(1), 17. https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-019-0228-7 • Gough, C.; Cunningham, R.; Mander, S. (2018): Understanding key elements in establishing a social license for CCS: An empirical approach. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 68, 16-25. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2017.12.011 • Glanz, S.; Schönauer, A.-L. (2021): Towards a Low-Carbon 		

¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0301421513001729>

	<p>Society via Hydrogen and Carbon Capture and Storage: Social Acceptance from a Stakeholder Perspective. <i>Journal of Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems</i>, 9(1), 9-19. https://doi.org/10.13044/j.sdewes.d8.0278</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wallquist, L.; Seigo, S.L.; Visschers, V.H.M.; Siegrist, M. (2012): Public acceptance of CCS system elements: A conjoint measurement. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 6, 77-83. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijggc.2011.10.007 • Broecks, K., Jack, C., Ter Mors, E., Boomsma, C., & Shackley, S. (2021): How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 81, 102236. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102236
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[1] Batel, S., Devine-Wright, P., & Tangeland, T. (2013). Social acceptance of low carbon energy and associated infrastructures: A critical discussion. *Energy Policy*, 58, 1-5.

[2] Witte, K. (2021). Social acceptance of carbon capture and storage (CCS) from industrial applications. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 12278.

[3] Whitmarsh, L.; Xenias, D.; Jones, C.R. Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage. *Palgrave Commun.* 2019, 5, 17.

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[5] Glanz, S.; Schönauer, A.-L. Towards a Low-Carbon Society via Hydrogen and Carbon Capture and Storage: Social Acceptance from a Stakeholder Perspective. *J. Sustain. Dev. Energy Water Environ. Syst.* 2021, 9, 9.

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